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Mobility of elements from tailings produced after flotation of low-grade, vanadium-bearing titanomagnetite deposit

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Study objectives

To investigate the mobilization of potentially hazardous elements (PHEs) present in tailings obtained from V-bearing titanomagnetite deposit processing.

To assess the environmental risk using standard leaching tests EN 12457-2, TCLP as well as pH dependence tests.

To evaluate the reliability of each test in predicting potential metal mobility.

To explore tailings valorisation options in line with circular economy principles.

Background

The EC Critical Raw Materials Act aims to reduce Europe's dependency on strategic/ CRMs imported from third countries.

Domestic extraction of V and Ti contributes to achieving the > 10% domestic extraction target.

Mining and metallurgical operations generate large volumes of waste with environmental impacts.

Improper waste management may affect soil, surface water and groundwater quality.

Raw material examined

Ilmenite flotation tailings produced at from ore processing at Otanmäki mine in Finland.

<https://www.otanmaki.fi/en/mining-project/>

EN 12457-2 and TCLP - Methodology

❖ EN 12457-2/ European Standard leaching test for characterization of waste and determining which can be disposed of at landfills.

❖ TCLP/ US EPA method. This method uses lower pH conditions to stimulate the worst-case leaching scenarios.

❖ The differences between these tests are the L/S ratio, the reagents and the stirring time.

pH dependent test- methodology

Sample preparation

85(wt%) less than 0.3 mm

Target pH values

pH (2 – 12)

Adjust pH (HNO_2 or NaOH or KOH)

Parallel extractions

L/S 10

24 h stirring

(As fraction particle diameter)

Separation

Liquid-Solid separation

Analysis

Determine concentration of metals in extract

Sequential extraction method by Tessier et. al. 1979

Exchangeable

8 mL MgCl_2 (pH7), 1 h Continuous agitation

Binds to Carbonates

1 M NaOAc (pH 5 acetic acid), 5 h continuous agitation

Bound to Fe-Mn oxides

0.04 M $\text{NH}_2\text{OH}\cdot\text{HCl}$ in 25% v/v HOAc, T=96 °C with occasional agitation

Bound to Organic Matter

a) 30 mL 0.02M HNO_3 +5mL 30% H_2O_2
(pH2)

b) 3 mL 30% H_2O_2 (pH2)

c) 3mL 3.2M NH_4OAc (20%v/v HNO_3)

Residual

a) HF: HClO_4 (5:1),

b) HF (10 mL): HClO_4 (1 mL)

c) HClO_4 (1 mL)

d) Dissolution 12 N HCl to 25 mL

Chemical analysis

Oxides - Elements	Concentration (wt%)	Oxides - Elements	Concentration (wt%)
Al₂O₃	15.35	Na₂O	1.31
As	<0.001	Ni	0.013
Ba	0.018	P	0.015
CaO	5.52	Pb	<0.001
Cl	0.079	S	0.0213
Co	0.012	SiO₂	28.9
Cr₂O₃	0.003	Sn	<0.001
Cu	0.011	Sr	0.03
Fe	17.3	TiO₂	9.83
K₂O	0.477	V	0.092
MgO	9.21	Zn	0.038
Mn	0.2	Zr	0.005

Mineralogical Analysis

Magnesio-hornblende 48%
Ilmenite 29%
Muscovite 15%
Chlorite 7%
Magnetite 1%

EN 12457-2 and TCLP results

- ✓ The leached concentration of **Ni and Zn exceed** the EN 12457-2 for acceptance in landfills of non-hazardous wastes (10 and 50 mg/kg)
- ✓ The leached concentrations for **Cu and Cr are well below** the respective limits.
- ✓ **TCLP** indicates some mobility for **Zn** and **Ni** (4 and 2.5 mg/L), however
- ✓ The **TCLP** test has limit only for **Cr** (5 mg/L)

pH dependent test - results

- ❖ All elements exhibit higher leaching rate at pH 2.
- ❖ increased leached concentrations for Ni, Co, Cu, Zn, Mn and Sr (pH < 6)
- ❖ the leached concentrations of V and Cr are very low at all pH values
- ❖ Ti leached conc. was lower than the Detection Limit in all pH values

Sequential extraction test

- ✓ Zn (147.5 mg/kg)
- ✓ Ni (52,1 mg/kg)
- ✓ V (43 mg/kg) and
- ✓ Cu (40 mg/kg)

○ Cr and Sr concentrations are lower than Detection Limit (DL)

Conclusions

The difference in leaching rates for the heavy metals studied in different toxicity tests is due to differences in test conditions (type of leaching solution, pH level, particle size and mineralogical composition of the waste).

The potential environmental impacts at disposal sites differ depending on the test used.

These findings suggest that current leaching protocols need to be revised or improved to ensure more accurate assessment of the mobility of PHEs from wastes and finally of the risk.

More leaching tests are needed to assess impacts on environmental media (e.g soil, surface- and groundwater).

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